

Discoveries[©]

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Abstract

Of the three branches of medicine, biophysics is the safest and easiest to use. Biochemistry is dangerous and psychology as a science almost useless yet important. Since Rockefeller corrupted the medical establishment over a hundred years ago, it has left the pharmaceutical industry controlling medicine with nothing to cure pain and chronic disease except brain blockers that leave patients half dead. Biophysics and the electrical properties of the body were always known and ignored until CellSonic, my company, was able to package all properties of light pressure and electrical field into one machine that anyone with commonsense could use safely. When a patient has failed to get help from their usual doctor, they find their way to a CellSonic clinic and are delighted to be cured or healed without side effects. Because the treatments are safe, only aiming into the ear is banned, the CellSonic is tried, and more often than not the result is an improvement almost immediately. This has led to discoveries that the establishment admits cannot be cured by their drugs. This article lists a few that have been reported to me in one month, August 2024.

The Pendulum

The pendulum is explained by [Dr Dickens in a video](#), scroll to the bottom of the page:

All CellSonic users are now checking patients with a pendulum and find it to be accurate. Exactly how it works is intriguing and is probably responding to the electrical properties of the body which are corrected by the electrical field emitted by the CellSonic pulse. [The inadequacy of science](#) is discussed in the article seen by clicking on the hyperlink. The pendulum reveals the behavior of cells, not the appearance which is what the establishment uses with scans and microscopes. When a cell voltage is lifted to its correct value of 75 mv its appearance does not change but its replication ceases to be profuse and reverts to the correct renewal of days and weeks. The definition of cancer is

the rapid profusion of cells. When that is stopped, the cells are not cancerous. They have shifted from malignant to benign. CellSonic makes that happen in about a minute, the time it takes to deliver 200 pulses.

The combination of a pendulum and CellSonic machine enables a diagnosis and correction of chronic disease, including cancer, in twenty minutes as explained in [the Sapiens Shield plan](#). The video by Jorge Curé explains the voltage of a cancer cell has to be your starting point in the understanding of cancer. Now go to the paper by Haltiwanger, [The Electrical Properties of Cancer Cells](#). When this becomes a standard text in all medical schools it will

mark the end of Rockefeller medicine and the end of much suffering and premature deaths. Then see the video from 1988 by Bjorn Nordenström on the Sapiens Shield page. Professor Nordenström had discovered that cancer is an electrical fault and even though he was the chairman of the Nobel Prize committee, the pinnacle of the establishment, he was still ridiculed and rejected, such is the power of Big Pharma.

The brain – pituitary gland

Here is a report from Patty Priestley in Idaho, USA about a patient with a tumor on the pituitary gland in her brain:

I met this woman, Virginia, on the first weekend in March of 2024. She was a complete mess. She had just finished yet another round of radiation pills that made her deathly sick. She had been living with migraines for years and she was battling a tumor within her pituitary gland that was enlarged and pressing on different parts of her brain. When she came into my clinic, we cleaned up her diet, got her to eat organic, and took the right supplements. She started on my other frequency machines. In April, I used the pendulum on her. I waited until April because we had to detox the radiation out. So in April, I used the CellSonic on her and it was showing

low energy in her temples, and the top of her head. We knew where the enlarged tumor gland was so we put pulses in through each temple. We did pulses through the top of her head and we went to the back of her head at the soft place at the top of the neck. In the first treatment in April, we did 200 pulses at level 4 in each spot and the pendulum was spinning positive after. We did another treatment toward the end of May. (We spread it out for cost reasons plus her next appointment with the doctor was going to be at the beginning of June so that's why we did the 2nd appointment at the end of May) We did her temples and the top of her head again. This time it was more sensitive so we needed fewer pulses. We only did 50 pulses at a level 2 in each spot using the more intense head. She had her blood work taken at the beginning of June and in July she was told her pituitary gland was operating at perfectly normal. She continues with maintenance on frequencies currently. She is free of headaches is no longer sick and has great energy.

The Brain – blood clots

This report from Denmark is shown on the CellSonic medical website as [an interview with Steen](#), the patient. The subtext is in English.

Cellsonic Treatment for Paralysis

Danish patient with brain damage improves after a 50 second CellSonic treatment. For ten years, he had no help from the hospitals.

In both brain cases, the pituitary and the blood clots, no drugs were used and there were no side effects. Both patients had received treatments from the establishment which were of no help. Having been failed by the white coats, Viginia and Steen found CellSonic and were corrected painlessly with CellSonic biophysics.

Musculoskeletal Pain

From: "Patty Priestley" <pattypriestley@yahoo.com>

Sent: Thu, Aug 15, 2024 at 4:01 PM

Subject: Testimonial to send to Andrew

This is a testimonial from Patty Priestley practitioner of the CellSonic at my clinic of Agape Healing and Wellness in Caldwell Idaho.

I have a client aged about 77 male with over 40 years of cellulitis with diabetic neuropathy. When he started with me his legs were completely numb and completely purple. I started him in July of 2023 on my first frequency

energy machine the Molecular Enhancer. Then in March of 2024, I got my second energy frequency machine he saw a little improvement with each machine. In April of 2024, I started having him apply Cypress essential oil to the bottoms of his feet with a slight improvement in feeling. Also in April 2024, I gave him his first Cellsonic treatment on his feet and up his legs to his knees. In one week's time, he had 50% of his normal pink color back. I've done two more treatments on his feet and legs about a month apart for cost reasons, and after each treatment, he's showing progress in color minimizing. At this writing mid-August of 2024, I plan on doing another treatment to the bottoms of his feet soon and also I will revisit any parts of the legs that still have any remaining color.

The story is significant because through his years of losing his feeling and mobility, he had to sell all of his equipment and cars that had clutches because he could not operate those and now he has enough feeling and mobility back that he is now driving a clutch Jeep and having big fun again.

Lisa Lotte in Denmark

Like the man in Patty's report, Lisa is diabetic, a condition that CellSonic can reverse by aiming at the pancreas to rejuvenate the Islets Langerhans allowing the person to make their own insulin again.

We see Lisa in [two videos taken twenty minutes apart](#), before and after the CellSonic treatment. A toe had been amputated which affects her walking.

Nevertheless, she walks better and painlessly after the treatment wondering what has happened to her to have been healed so quickly.

CellSonic emits three forces: light, pressure, and electrical field. Of these three, it seems that the one causing the most change is the electrical field. This is explained in the article, [The Handheld Thunderstorm](#).

This translation of comments by Lisa was added to a media site.

Gregers Brinch

Before treatment she was suffering from multiple symptoms. Body pained and utterly stiff. Depressed, insomnia, joints seized up. Walk was robot like. The 5 minute treatment resulted significant positive changes....even the sugar craving has abated. Far better hearing and vision. She describes a kind of realignment.

Fungus

Report from Denmark. Jorgen's hand last December was infected with fungus. He had been infected for many years and got no help from anyone anywhere until he found CellSonic.

A week after one treatment, the infected layer was falling off and clear skin emerging.

Five months later his hands were clearing.

By the end of August 2024, the clearing continues.

But, as well as his hands, at the outset his feet had been worse. The fungus layer was thicker.

Six months later, in June 2024, the fungus broke up showing how thick it had become. I have instructed you to not pick off pieces of the dead fungus. The CellSonic treatment has killed the infection, whatever it was, and new skin is forming. The outer, dead layer will come off when it is ready.

By late August the fungus continues to fall off the heels.

Melanoma

Whilst Jorgen was being treated, his wife watched. She had melanoma on her forehead and did not want CellSonic so the therapist, Jette Breitenstein, used a simpler machine from the CellSonic family to deliver 35 volts through the surface of the skin. It does not penetrate. It is called Time Machine and can be seen at <https://www.cellsenic-beauty.com/wrinkles.htm>. The voltage was enough to convert the melanoma to benign. The lump still sat there changing colour and gradually lifting away. The lady did the treatment herself holding one electrode on the lump and the other an inch away so that current flowed through the lump. She held it there for about twenty minutes and had no

discomfort. Time Machine is low enough in cost for home use compared to the CellSonic machine which is usually used in clinics.

By late August 2024, the fingers are almost clear, the heels are clearing and the melanoma lump is still attached but not cancerous. It could detach any day when new skin has formed below and releases its protective cover. No drugs have been used, only CellSonic and Time machine. The patients felt no pain or side effects.

Lichen Sclerosus

Our skin is external and internal. The external is obviously on the outside and gets a lot of attention because we can see it. Internal skin is in the mouth, anus, and vagina hidden from sight but equally as sensitive and maybe more sensitive. On the external skin, there can be [psoriasis](#), an autoimmune disease often triggered by stress. CellSonic has had significant success with psoriasis.

When news arrived from Denmark about lichen sclerosis, it was a discovery that quickly seemed to be similar to psoriasis but on internal skin. All the patients attending Jette Breitenstein's clinic had sought help from their health service in Denmark and found it to be useless. The only treatment was a steroid cream that thins the internal skin making the problem worse.

Jette applies pulses at energy level 10 aimed into the vagina where there are no bones, only soft tissues. She usually books patients for six sessions and finds that after three sessions they do not need further treatment. They all have different additional issues, some with a bladder infection, maybe the anus is affected and some have psoriasis. Most have stress and our insight is that the stress causes the lichen sclerosis with, of course, the lichen

increasing the stress. Where is the start of this vicious circle? It is difficult to be told to not think about the pain and itching that does not go away. Mind control is difficult. Think about food and you become hungry. Be distracted and you forget food.

We also observe in connection with sensitivity that there is a direct correlation with intelligence. More brain power is more ability to see dangers and consequences so the bright people get stressed more than the happy-go-lucky.

There are no reliable statistics on the prevalence of the disease. Some say one in seventy and others say it is much more common. The problem is that it is not talked about Search on the internet for lichen sclerosis. A lot of information is available with no cures and the bad advice to use a steroid cream.

Conclusion

The surest way to stop chronic disease developing, including cancer, is to find it before a person knows they have it. This can be done with the Sapiens Shield plan. It saves suffering and an enormous amount of money because it stops people from becoming ill and the diagnosing and curing can be done by nurses in street corner drop-in centers.

Stress is a common cause of illness. The science of psychology has degenerated into blocking the brain with drugs that never cure. Anti-depressants should be illegal. Psychology has to accept that humans are gregarious and need companionship and conversation. Insights into anxieties are the way forward for psychiatrists, not administering drugs.

By assembling all forces of biophysics into one easy-to-use machine, CellSonic has enabled all countries to have a medical system that makes people well at a low cost.

References

1. Dr Dickens in a video
2. The inadequacy of science
3. the Sapiens Shield plan
4. The Electrical Properties of Cancer Cells
5. an interview with Steen
6. two videos taken twenty minutes apart
7. The Handheld Thunderstorm
8. <https://www.cellsonic-beauty.com/wrinkles.htm>
9. psoriasis